

PROVISION WITH MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN THE COLLECTION AND PROCESSING OF FIELD ETHNOGRAPHIC MATERIALS.

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Annotation. This article discusses the methods used in the collection of field ethnographic materials and the role of modern technology used in it and their advantages.

Keywords. Expedition, photography, informant, video camera, TV studio.

The main methods of ethnographic study of everyday culture are observation and interviews. Ethnographers go on expeditions (in the field), where they collect field materials. These can be records of observations and conversations with the local population, drawings, drawings, visual material (photos and video materials) that record both objects of material culture and aspects and phenomena of socio- normative and spiritual cultures. If possible, household items are collected in the field, which in the future become ethnographic exhibits in museums.

During expeditions, ethnographers use the following methods of collecting ethnographic material:

1. Direct (personal) observation (of an object, informant, rite, process).
2. Interviewing (survey) (survey according to the program or questionnaire, in-depth (open) interview), questioning.
- 3) Identification and fixation of material sources.
- 4) Identification and processing of documentary materials.

To date, in order to carry out the above tasks, to collect high-quality documentary materials, an ethnographer needs to use modern technologies.

A little earlier, ethnographic expeditions were equipped with analog photo, audio, and video equipment, which meant that the materials were limited by the number of photographic films and audio and video cassettes and the impossibility of working with them immediately during the expedition.

Today, modern digital technology provides much more opportunities in field work. Capacious laptop hard drives and external hard drives remove the limitation in the number of photo, audio, video files and allow you to work with them already in the field: select by quality, rename files according to the numbering of field documentation. That is, it gives a great opportunity in the collection and processing of field ethnographic materials.

Ethnographers have been using a camera for quite a long time, and today not a single expedition usually does without photography. You can take pictures of everything: residential and outbuildings, the interior of the hut, household items, costume, as well as the main points of ritual culture. A photograph taken in the field today is not only an illustration of the study, but also an independent ethnographic source.

Compiling ethnographic atlases and photo albums requires detailed and accurate photographic recording of complex objects, which can only be done using professional digital equipment, and only by professional operators. This work requires a significant amount of time, so it should be done by separate people.

If earlier shooting of ethnographic stories was carried out, as a rule, by television studios, television companies, today ethnographers themselves have taken the camera into their hands. But there is a bad side to using this technique, where the person himself, who is in front of the video camera, behaves somewhat differently than in a simple conversation, many are afraid of shooting and therefore behave constrainedly, in some cases they are not allowed to turn on the camera at all.

With the help of audio recordings, conversations with informants can be verbatim recorded. Professionally made audio recordings reproduce not only the exact performance of folklore, both in speech and musical form, but also the phonetic features of the language and dialect. Audio sound is a great addition to the texts of transcripts of audio recordings.

Another advantage of modern technology is the field documentation system, which allows you to quickly document very large digital photo, scan, audio, and video materials right in the field.

One of the last works of field ethnographic work is the cameral processing of the collected materials, which also requires the use of modern technologies. In the process of cameral processing, material is selected by quality, renaming each file in accordance with the expedition numbering, a text description of each file, combining files into thematic groups or splitting files into plots. For example, photographic materials are combined into thematic groups, while audio materials, on the contrary, are divided into plots during transcription. Thus, the materials are prepared for subsequent archiving.

In conclusion, I would like to note that the current level of digital technology makes it possible to create a completely new type of field source that reflects the realities of culture in many ways. Also, the use of the achievements of modern technology accelerates the pace of collecting field information, allows you to collect a large amount of information in a short time, and significantly reduce the time of field work.

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